

SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION : A COMPARISON BETWEEN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS IN SHIMLA

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of this paper is to compare the quality of service, from the perspective customers, between public and private sector banks in Shimla. Employee behavior instill confidence in customers is more in private sector banks. It has also been found that private sector banks are more willing to help their customers and are consistently polite with them. Public sector banks are doing a good job in catering to all groups of the society instead of serving to the upper income group. It has been observed that private sector banks do not caters to all income group of the society. Both banks take sincere interest in solving customer's problems.

Keywords : customer, confidence, politeness, customer satisfaction, interest

INTRODUCTION

Banks play a major role in the growth of any country. A bank is a financial entity that accepts deposits and uses those funds to lend directly or through capital markets. It links consumers who have capital shortages with customers who have capital surpluses. (Khan, 2015) Quality service, customer happiness, customer retention, and customer loyalty are major issues faced by the Indian banking sector. In the banking industry, quality service is important to attaining customer happiness and building brand loyalty.

The onset of competition from the private players and initiation of banking reforms since early 1990s have led to an increased emphasis on efficient customer service. The banking industry is facing rapid changes in the market, such as: new technologies, economic uncertainties, fierce competition, more demanding customers and the changing climate which lead to an unprecedented set of challenges. Banking is a customer-oriented service industry which has witnessed a radical shift in the market power. Customer service is a dynamic interactive process which needs continuous

improvement. With the advancement of information technology and communication system, the whole world has been reduced to a global village. Measuring service quality, particularly in the banking industry, is more challenging task than measuring the quality of goods. The service sector as a whole is extremely heterogeneous, and what is diverse for one service may not be true for another. (Nagabhushanam, 2011).

DATA COLLECTION

The collection of data has been based on primary probe. The primary data were collected from customers of public and private sector banks with the help of questionnaire. In present study, some questionnaire was personally distributed to respondents and after filled by them, questionnaire was collected from the respondents and some were sent to respondent through mail.

STATISTICAL TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS:

The collected data was coded and tabulated before it was given statistical treatment. Statistical tools like percentage and chi-square were used with the help of SPSS to derive conclusion and results.

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PART I – RESPONDENT'S PROFILE

The customers of the banks residing in Shimla city were the respondents of this survey. The data has captured

customers of four different banks such as SBI, PNB, ICICI and HDFC. The profile of the various customers has been described below.

Table-1.1: Classification of Respondents on The Basis of Age Group

Age Group	No. of Respondents	Percentage
LESS THAN 20	4	4%
20-30	52	47%
30-40	24	22%
ABOVE 40	30	27%
TOTAL	110	100%

Source: Field survey 2019

It is observed from table -1.1 that respondents which are less than 20 are just 4 percent. Whereas, the majority of the respondents i.e. 47 percent fall under the age group ranging from 20 to 30 years. Only, 22

percentage of respondents fall under in between the age group of 30 to 40 years and 27 percent belong to the age group that is above 40 years.

Table-1.2: Classification of Respondents on The Basis of Gender

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
MALE	62	56%
FEMALE	48	44%
TOTAL	110	100%

Source: Field survey 2019

It is observed from table-1.2 that male respondents are in majority which is 56 percent and female

respondents are just 44 percent out of the total 110 respondents.

Table-1.3: Classification of Respondents on The Basis of Educational Qualification

Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
SEN. SEC. /HR. SEC.	14	13%
GRADUATE	55	50%
POST GRADUATE AND ABOVE	41	37%
TOTAL	110	100%

Source: Field survey 2019

It is observed from table-1.3 that 50 percent of the respondents are graduates which has the majority of

concentration. 37 percent of the respondents are post graduates and above and only 13 percent were found to be in senior secondary/higher secondary category.

Table-1.4: Classification of Respondents on The Basis of Type of Bank

Type of Bank	No. of Respondents	Percentage
PUBLIC SECTOR BANK	79	72%
PRIVATE SECTOR BANK	31	28%
TOTAL	110	100%

Source: Field survey 2019

As per the above table-1.4 the majority of respondents have opened their bank accounts in a public sector bank i.e. 79 which accounts for 62 percent of the

total 110 respondents and only 28 percent have bank accounts in a private sector bank.

PART II - AN EVALUATION OF PERCEPTION OF CUSTOMERS

Table- 2.1: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Modern Equipment

Type of Bank	Modern equipment			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	23(29.1)	47(59.5)	9(11.4)	79(100)
Private sector	16(51.6)	14(45.2)	1(3.2)	31(100)
Total	39(35.5)	61(55.5)	10(9.1)	110(100)

Chi-Square = 5.637

DF= 2

P. Value=0.050

Source: Field survey 2019

It is demonstrated from the table that the majority of respondents accounting for about 59.5 percent of public sector banks and 51.6 percent of private sector banks were agree that there is modern equipment in banks. There are only 11.4 percent respondents in public

sector banks and 3.2 percent in private sector banks which are not supporting that banks have modern equipment. The calculated value of chi square (5.637) is more than the table value at 5 percent level of significance.

Table- 2.2: Type of Bank and Their Opinion Regarding Physical Facilities Visually Appealing

Type of Bank	Physical facilities visually appealing			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	18 (22.8)	46 (58.2)	15 (19)	79 (100)
Private sector	11 (35.5)	18 (58.1)	2 (6.5)	31 (100)
Total	29 (26.4)	64 (58.2)	17 (15.5)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 3.626

DF = 2

P. Value= 0.163

Source: Field survey 2019

Note: The figures in parenthesis depict percentage.

It is manifested from the table that the majority of respondents accounting for about 58.2 percent of public sector banks and 58.1 percent of private sector banks were agree that there are physical facilities visually appealing in banks. There are only 19 percent respondents in public sector banks and 6.5 percent in

private sector banks which are not supporting that banks have appealing physical facilities. The calculated value of chi square (3.626) is less than the table value at 5 percent level of significance. It shows an insignificant result at 5 percent level of significance which further states that there is no relationship between types of banks and the attribute 'physical facilities visually appealing'.

Table- 2.3: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Employees have a Neat Appearance

Type of Bank	Employee have a neat appearance			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	22 (27.8)	44 (55.7)	13 (16.5)	79 (100)
Private sector	18 (58.1)	13 (41.9)	0 (0)	31 (100)
Total	40 (36.4)	57 (51.8)	13 (11.8)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 11.505

DF = 2

P. Value = 0.003

Source: Field survey 2019

It is manifested from this table that the majority of respondents accounting for about 55.7 percent agree that employee have a neat appearance in public sector banks. There are only 16.5 percent respondents which are not supporting that employees of public sector banks have

neat appearance. On the other hand, 58.1 percent of the total respondents strongly agree that employees have neat appearance in private sector banks. The p-value is less than 0.05 which means there is association between types of banks and the attribute 'employees have a neat appearance'.

Table- 2.4: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Promises to do The Work Timely

Type of Bank	Promises to do the work timely			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	17 (21.5)	44 (55.7)	18 (22.8)	79 (100)
Private sector	12 (38.7)	14 (46.2)	5 (16.1)	31 (100)
Total	29 (28.4)	58 (52.7)	23 (20.9)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 3.436

DF = 2

P. Value = 0.179

Source: Field survey 2019

Note: The figures in parenthesis depict percentage.

It is manifested from the table that the majority of the respondents accounting for about 55.7 percent falling in the group of public sector bank agree with the statement of promises to do the work timely. There are 21.5 percent respondents who are strongly agreeing with the above statement. On the other hand, there are 46.2 percent respondents in the group of private sector banks

who are agreeing that promises to do in time are fulfilled by private sector banks. The aggregate distribution of respondents shows that 52.7 percent of the total respondents agree with the above statement. The calculated value of chi-square 3.436 is less than the table value at 5 percent level of significance.

Table- 2.5: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Sincere Interest in Solving Customer's Problems

Type of Bank	Sincere interest in solving customer's problems			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	21 (26.6)	45 (57)	13 (16.5)	79 (100)
Private sector	13 (41.9)	13 (41.9)	5 (16.1)	31 (100)
Total	34 (30.9)	58 (52.7)	18 (16.4)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 2.653

DF = 2

P. Value = 0.265

Source: Field survey 2019

It is manifested from the table that the majority of the respondents accounting for about 57 percent falling in the group of public sector bank agree to the above statement. There are only 16.5 percent respondents in the public sector banks who are not supporting with the above statement. On the other hand, in the group of

private sector banks 41.9 percent respondents strongly agree and the same percentage respondents agree with the above statement. The aggregate distribution of respondents shows that 52.7 percent respondents agree with the above statement.

Table- 2.6: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Bank Inform When Services will be Performed

Type of Bank	Banks inform when services will be performed			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	30 (38)	31 (39.2)	18 (22.8)	79 (100)
Private sector	16 (51.6)	15 (48.4)	0 (0)	31 (100)
Total	46 (41.8)	46 (41.8)	18 (16.4)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 8.499

DF = 2

P. Value = 0.014

Source: Field survey 2019

It is manifested from the table that the majority i.e. 51.6 percent of the total respondents falling in the group of private sector banks strongly agrees with the above statement. There is no respondent in the group of private sector banks who are not satisfied with this attribute of service provided by banks. In the group of public sector banks 39.2 percent respondents agree with the above statement. In total 41.8 percent of the total respondents

strongly agree and the same percentage of respondents pertaining to this group agrees to the above statement. The calculated value of chi-square test is 8.499 is with p value 0.014 which is less than 0.05 which rejects the null hypothesis at 5 percent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between type of bank and the attribute bank inform when services will be provided.

Table- 2.7: Type of Bank and Their Responses Regarding Bank's Willingness to Help Customers

Type of Bank	Willingness to help customers			Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	
Public sector	12 (15.2)	46 (58.2)	21 (26.6)	79 (100)
Private sector	16 (51.6)	15 (48.4)	0 (0)	31 (100)
Total	28 (25.5)	61 (55.5)	21 (19.1)	110 (100)

Chi-Square = 20.223

DF = 2

P. Value = 0.000

Source: Field survey 2019

It is manifested from this table that the majority of respondents accounting for about 58.2 percent agree that employees of public sector banks are willing to help their customers. There are only 26.6 percent respondents who are not supporting that employees of public sector banks have a willingness to help customers. On the other hand, 51.6 percent of the total respondents strongly agree that employees of private sector banks are willing to help customers and 0 percent of the respondents do not support this statement. The calculated value of chi square (20.223) is more than the table value at 5 percent level of significance. It shows a significant result at 5 percent level of significance which further states that there is a relationship between types of banks and the attribute 'willingness to help customers.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- It has been observed that private sector banks are more equipped with modern equipment's in comparison to public sector banks.
- Employee behavior instill confidence in customers is more in private sector banks. It has been found that private sector banks are more willing to help their customers and are consistently polite with them.
- Public sector banks are doing a good job in catering to all groups of the society instead of serving to the upper income group. It has been observed that private sector banks do not caters to all income group of the society. Both banks take sincere interest in solving customer's problems.

- Physical facilities are more visually appealing in private sector banks and majority of the respondents feel that employees of private sector banks have a neat appearance. It can be said that private sector banks are a step ahead of public sector banks in understanding the specific needs of the customers.
- Both type of banks are competing equally with each-other, but private sector banks are a little bit below the line in providing trustworthy services. Respondents trust public sector banks in comparison to private sector banks.
- In respect to the promise for doing work in time private sector banks lags behind from public sector banks and also it has been analyzed that private banks give individual attention to their customers. Both banks make their customers feel secure with their banking services.
- It has been analyzed from the data that private bank immediately informs when services will be performed while in this context public sector banks, they are a step behind.

References :

1. Bedi, M. (2010). An integrated framework for service quality, customer satisfaction and behavioral responses in Indian banking industry-A comparison of public and private sector banks. *Journal of Services Research*, 10 (1), 157-172.
2. Kamath, B. (2010). Measuring Service Quality (SERVQUAL) in Banks. *Prajnan: Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 39(1), 41-52.
3. Khan , M. Y. (2015). *Indian Financial System*. Chennai : McGraw Hill Education.
4. Manimaran, S. (2010). Linkage between Service Quality and Customers Loyalty in Commercial Banks. *Journal of Marketing and Communication*, 6(1), 26-34.
5. Nagabhushanam, M. (2011). A study on customer service quality of banks in India. *Journal of Analyz Research Solutions*, 315-364.
6. Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. (1988). *SERVQUAL: A multiple item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. Journal of Retailing*, 64 (1), 12-40.
7. Paul, S. (2013). An Assessment of Service Quality of Commercial Banks in Odisha. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 4(6), 1446-1451.
8. Rao, R. M., and Lakew, T. B. (2011). Service Quality Perceptions of Customers: A Study of The Customers' of Public Sector and Private Sector Commercial Banks in India. *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management* 2(11), 13-16.
9. Srivastava, S.P., Khanna, R. & Mukherjee, R. (2019). A Comparative Study of Service Dimensions of private and Public Sector Banks. *Journal of Critical Review*, 6(4), 156-163.

